

OVERVIEW OF THE KAZAKHSTAN MARKET FOR PERFUMERY AND COSMETIC PRODUCTS

Turuspayeva Zh.Zh.
Zhumashova G.T.

Kazakh national medical university named by S. D. Asfendiyarov, Almaty city,
Republic of Kazakhstan

e-mail: turuspaeva2002@mail.kz

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17332993>

Relevance: in the context of globalisation and the tightening of technical regulations of the Eurasian Economic Union TR 009/2011, it is important to analyse the market structure, consumer preferences and the potential for localising the production of cosmetic products.

Purpose of the study: to conduct a comprehensive analysis of the current state of the perfume and cosmetics market in Kazakhstan, identify key trends and prospects for the development of local production and exports.

Materials and methods: data from the Medical and Pharmaceutical Control Committee of the Republic of Kazakhstan for January-October 2024, production and import statistics, as well as a sample from the Unified Register of State Registration Certificates of the Eurasian Economic Union (63,768 products as of 06.04.2025) were used. Methods of comparative analysis and classification of products by functional groups (creams, gels, serums, etc.) were applied.

Results: the analysis showed that the volume of cosmeceutical production in Kazakhstan for the first ten months of 2024 amounted to 5,679.4 tonnes (+6.6% compared to 2023), while imports amounted to 57,395.2 tonnes. The most frequently registered product categories were: creams (14,092), gels (8,140), shampoos (2,838), conditioners (2,819) and serums (2,208). Amendments to Eurasian Economic Union Technical Regulation 009/2011, which came into force in 2024, tightened safety requirements (Mean Opinion Score factor ≥ 100) and labelling requirements. An imbalance was identified between the distribution role of local companies and the lack of a developed production base.

Conclusions: the Kazakh cosmetics and personal care products market remains dependent on imports, but has significant growth potential. To strengthen its position in the Eurasian Economic Union market and enter international markets, it is necessary to:

- stimulate scientific research and investment in the cosmeceuticals sector.
- develop production infrastructure and export capacity.
- harmonise standards with International Organization for Standardization, and Eurasian Economic Union requirements.
- promote the development of competitive national brands.

The implementation of these measures will enable Kazakhstan not only to reduce its dependence on imports, but also to occupy a sustainable niche in the regional and global beauty industry.